

PROBLEMS IN TRANSLATING ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS INTO ENGLISH

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Abstract. Most new concepts both in the Russian and English languages are expressed using phrases or compound words, because such complex words make it possible to represent a particular concept with completeness and accuracy. But multi component terms—complex words and phrases— are cumbersome; therefore, there is a need to abbreviate them in one way or another. In some cases this leads to the use of short versions of the term in the form of only one main component, while in others, various types of abbreviations are used, which can save time. However, their imprecise or incorrect translation can change or confuse the intended meaning. The paper discusses the differences in using abbreviations and acronyms in British and American scientific texts, as well as difficulties of their translation and optimal strategies of inter language adaptation. The investigation is performed using various research techniques, including a comparative method, a continuous sampling method, semantic structure analysis, and contextual analysis. It is shown that the existing modern classifications of abbreviations greatly differ in linguistic scientific literature and lexical units are abbreviated using various methods. It is found that there exist various traditions of their usage in scientific and technical texts. It is demonstrated that various standards for introducing, spelling, and punctuating abbreviations and acronyms in British and American scientific journals pose additional difficulties in the work of a translator in the field of science and technology, provokes translation errors and requires the use of normalization and explication as the main strategies for their translation.

Keywords: acronyms, abbreviation; semantics; context; language universal

1.Introduction.

Over the past decades modern languages have exhibited a tendency towards ‘economical use,’ which consists in providing a maximum amount of data transmission per unit of time. In this regard, we currently observe an “explosive increase in the use of abbreviations” in languages. This is especially obvious in the language of science and technology, which is characterized by a large number of different types of abbreviations and acronyms. The growing number of abbreviations, which find use in modern languages, is quite natural.

Abbreviations are an important component of many scientific and technical papers, and if one uses them effectively, they not only reduce space, but also facilitate the reading and understanding of a text. Translators often face complex sentences that are abundant in terms for which we already have well-established shortened forms. An important feature of modern scientific and technical language is the large number of abbreviations and acronyms. For example, the sentence ‘Because X-ray computed tomography is the most common form of computed tomography in medicine and various other contexts, the term computed tomography alone is often used to refer to X-ray computed tomography, although other types exist (such as positron emission tomography and single-photon emission computed tomography).

2. Main part.

The existing methods of computed tomography and magnetic resonance tomography, including diffuse optical tomography, require a large rapid-access memory and considerable computational resources’ will be easier understood by scientists if appropriate abbreviations are introduced. Of course, the advantages of such an “economical use” will be obvious, provided the abbreviations have been defined previously in the text, in accordance with the scientific writing rules, or if use is made of occasional abbreviations, in compliance with the house style of a scientific journal. When voiced, the time of their pronunciation is much shorter than the corresponding concept, and when written, ‘their effect’ is even more impressive: ‘Because X-ray CT is the most common form of CT in medicine and various other contexts, the term CT alone is often used to refer to Xray CT, although other types exist (such as PET and SPECT). The existing methods of CT and MRT, including DOT, require a large RAM and considerable computational resources.’ From these examples we can see that if abbreviations are used in the above sentences, the text is reduced by about 1.25 times (69 words vs. 54 words). This demonstrates that abbreviations and acronyms are an important part of scientific articles and scientific and technical translation. Their proper use not only reduces space, but also facilitates the process of perception of a scientific text, which otherwise would be too long and difficult to read. Thus, in this paper we consider the characteristic features of abbreviations and acronyms in scientific texts. The rules that we cover in this piece of writing are not necessarily a review of all possible options which one might consider, but provide practical examples we have encountered in the course of our work as linguists and translators.

A variety of abbreviations and acronyms can be found in academic and professional texts. Because they are quite often registered in lexicographical sources, they can be considered lexical units of scientific and technical language. In the English language, abbreviations, according to their graphical and sound representation, are usually divided into abbreviations and acronyms. According to the online Oxford English Dictionary, an abbreviation is a shortened form of a word or phrase, for example, etc. for et cetera, e.g. for *exempli gratia*, kV for kilovolt, W for Watt, J for Joule, etc. In the same dictionary an acronym is an abbreviation formed from the initial letters of other words and pronounced as a single word [for example, laser (Light Amplification by Stimulated Emission of Radiation) or COIL (Chemical Oxygen–Iodine Laser)]. Despite the fact that acronyms and abbreviations are generally formed from combinations of capital letters, they can also be composed of lowercase letters, or even consist of capital and lowercase letters together, for example, mRNA (messenger ribonucleic acid), nsOCT (nano-sensitive optical coherence tomography), dBx (decibels above reference coupling) or ppb (parts per billion).

Thus, we can conclude that in modern linguistics there exist multiple classifications of abbreviations. Nevertheless, they can be mainly divided into abbreviations and acronyms, blends, graphic shortenings and clippings. It should be noted, however, that between these types of shortened words there are a number of border phenomena in which the shortening, after certain phonetic and morphological changes, undergoes a transition from one type to another. Of greatest interest to us are abbreviations and acronyms because blends, clippings and graphical shortenings do not seem difficult to use and translate. Abbreviations and acronyms, despite the fact that both are formed from the initial letters of a phrase, have one important difference: abbreviations may not be pronounced as a single word. This fact causes the difference in the use of abbreviations and acronyms in language and speech. It is also important that in some cases it is impossible to determine whether the shortened word is an acronym or an abbreviation and whether this or that phrase can be shortened. For example, Wikipedia recommends using abbreviations WWII or WW2 for the Second World War, while the Stylebook and Briefing on Media Law [9] and the Chicago Manual of Style do not recommend the use of abbreviations in this case. For example, an abbreviation is sometimes formed from an initial sound rather than from an initial letter of the terminological phrases (such as X in XML, extensible markup language), or from the application of a number (W3C, World Wide Web Consortium). In addition, acronyms and abbreviations are sometimes combined into a single word (JPEG, the first letter is spelled out and the subsequent

letters form the acronym). Sometimes it is impossible to distinguish between abbreviations and acronyms (FAQ, for example, can be pronounced as a word and spelled out).

The above explanation allows us to conclude that abbreviations are any shortened forms of the word, and acronyms are abbreviations pronounced as words [for example, AIDS (acquired immune deficiency syndrome)]. Of course, a scientist writing a scientific or technical paper probably does not need to know the difference between these two concepts, but for linguists and translators this misunderstanding and ignorance may lead to misuse of terms and inadequate translation.

3. Conclusion.

Nowadays the language of scientific and technical literature both in Russian and English often makes use of a large number of abbreviations and acronyms. Abridgement as a trend has become quite popular and common in many languages. The development of science and technology and international integration processes give rise to the appearance of new concepts which are expressed with the help of phrases and compound words. However, such phrases and compound words can be quite cumbersome, which leads to their abridgement. The use of abbreviations and acronyms in national languages is often justified because abridgements can save time, but their inadequate translation or use can be a cause of an error in translation. Abbreviations invade the everyday speech of certain social groups and are registered in various specialized dictionaries, including electronic sources. This makes it possible not only to study but also to analyze the course of the abbreviated word formation by native speakers. Thus, in this paper, we have discussed some important points regarding the use of abbreviations in scientific journals. In addition, we have provided guidance for using abbreviations in general and scholarly writing. Therefore, the topic of research can be interesting not only for linguists but also for a wider readership, including those who translate scientific texts for American and British readership. The authors wish to thank their colleague Stephen Garratt (England) for his helpful suggestions on manuscript editing and polishing the language of the paper.

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